

ETIOLOGY AND EPIDEMIOLOGY OF SEXUAL DISEASES

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Psychogenic sexual disorders, their etiopathogenesis, methods of treatment of patients with this disease have been of interest to scientists for a long time. One of the reasons for such high interest is that disorders are becoming more common. One of the most frequently observed types of sexual disorders is erectile dysfunction, the frequency of which increases with age. In young men, 5-8% are 75-80% at the age of 80. In particular, in the USA this pathology is observed in more than 10 million men, in Germany - in 3-5 million, in Russia-in about 6 million men. Therefore, the identification and treatment of patients with psychogenic sexual disorders, the improvement of medical and psychological assistance to them, along with basic treatment, is one of the urgent problems of modern medicine.

Purpose The purpose is to develop modern methods of treatment types of sexual disorders.

Materials and methods of research:

The data obtained from various medical institutions are also not reliable enough, as well as the data obtained as a result of direct examination of patients. This is due, firstly, to the fact that patients hide their sexual problems, and, secondly, the data obtained depend on the clinical qualifications of the researcher. thirdly, due to the fact that among sex therapists of different schools there are different points of view on the issues of diagnosis and research methods of sexual disorders. The fact that sexual problems are common among men can be judged, for example, by the data of one of the most representative sexual studies in the USA on social life and health.

Behavioral Health in the United States and Social Life (NHSL). The survey showed that a decrease or lack of interest in sexual activity is observed in 16% of men, In 19% of cases, insufficient erection is not observed and occurs very quickly 29% of respondents indicated the beginning of ejaculation and orgasm. Most men seek sexological help related to erectile dysfunction. The frequency of erectile dysfunction increases with age, from 5 to 8% in young men and by the age of 80 it reaches 75-80%. According to WHO, every Tenth person over the age of 21 suffers from erectile dysfunction, and every A third man over the age of 60 cannot have sex at all. In recent decades, the predominant sex treatment is a combination of various methods of psychotherapy, most often prescription drugs, physiotherapy effect, etc. This is a complex therapy it is often used in the form of special treatment programs. I. Kemper (1994) widely uses the compound in his work group psychoanalysis and methods of sex therapy. And in Unlike most foreign specialists, he does not have not only a couple, but also individual patients, for example , the disagreement of a partner pair therapy is impossible. on the basis of " behind every sexual disorder there is a communication disorder associated with a partner, it becomes obvious that psychotherapy without a partner is at least difficult. But it is still possible because the therapist is also a partner communication and the possibility of a mixed group of patients of both sexes is much higher than the possibilities of individual therapy". From other psychotherapeutic approaches to the correction of sexual desire in

dysfunctions M. Separately, Erickson's strategic therapy should be highlighted, he actively used methods and techniques developed by Clinical hypnosis for the treatment of people experiencing difficulties in sexual life

Research results: The patients were divided into 3 to achieve the objectives of the study Therapeutic groups of 40 people. Treatment of patients of the first group Performed by one of the phosphodiesterase type 5 inhibitors - vardenafil hydrochloride, patients of the second group – cognitive behavioral psychotherapy and the third group of patients-a combination of psychotherapeutic methods and vardenafil hydrochloride. The follow-up period during therapy was 8 weeks and 3-12 months after the end of treatment. The average age of the patients was 32.4 ± 8.7 years. Among them Men ($p < 0.05$) aged 19-29 years (45.8%) prevailed, who showed a sharp reaction of guys Sexual dysfunction compared to older men.

Conclusions: Average duration of sexual dysfunction in patients 34.1 ± 20.2 months (in addition, 32.5% of them had sexual problems from the beginning of sexual life). In patients ($P < 0.001$), people predominated, the duration of sexual dysfunction ranged from 13 to 36 months (43.3%). The data obtained show that one of the factors contributing to the development of neurotic disorders is prolonged Sexual dysfunction, prolonged traumatic effects (with 77.5%) patients previously unsuccessfully treated by other specialists). In an acute experimental situation with basic sex in case of dysfunction, patients turn to different persons, actively seeking help from specialists. Treatment without taking into account individual characteristics, the partner situation and the nature of mental pathology turned out to be ineffective, which forced men to seek other medical institutions.

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